

Security Oriented Nexus for Intelligent Commodity solutions marketplace.

PRESS RELEASE #1

Launching a Smart Marketplace for Advanced Cybersecurity Resilience

The **SONIC** project is proud to announce its official launch in Athens Greece. Funded by the European Union under the Digital Europe Programme, this 36-month initiative brings together 11 partners to develop an **intelligent marketplace** for "easy-to-deploy" containerized cybersecurity tools.

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The SONIC Marketplace Vision

- ✓ **Active Cybersecurity Suite:** Integrating threat intelligence and automated response.
- ✓ **Vulnerability Management:** AI-driven code repair and penetration testing.
- ✓ **Data Privacy:** Using homomorphic encryption for secure analysis.

The Consortium

Led by ISI, the consortium includes experts from *Greece, Cyprus, Spain, Germany, Estonia, Netherlands and Ireland.*

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